

HYBRID DATA APPROACH FOR SELECTING EFFECTIVE TEST CASES DURING THE REGRESSION TESTING

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Abstract- In the software industry, software testing becomes more important in the entire software development life cycle. Software testing is one of the fundamental components of software quality assurances. Software Testing Life Cycle (STLC) is a process involved in testing the complete software, which includes Regression Testing, Unit Testing, Smoke Testing, Integration Testing, Interface Testing, System Testing & etc. In the STLC of Regression testing, test case selection is one of the most important concerns for effective testing as well as cost of the testing process. During the Regression testing, executing all the test cases from existing test suite is not possible because that takes more time to test the modified software. This paper proposes new Hybrid approach that consists of modified Greedy approach for handling the test case selection and Genetic Algorithm uses effective parameter like Initial Population, Fitness Value, Test Case Combination, Test Case Crossover and Test Case Mutation for optimizing the tied test suite. By doing this, effective test cases are selected and minimized the tied test suite to reduce the cost of the testing process. Finally the result of proposed approach compared with conventional greedy approach and proved that our approach is more effective than other existing approach.

Index terms: Software Testing, Regression Testing, Test Reduction, Test Optimization, Test Data Generation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Software Testing is the process of evaluation of the product to achieve the expected performance of the product to meet the required performance. Software testing involves execution of a system component or software component to validate one or more functions to identify the fault or detect the fault. The need of software testing is important or main part of the software evolution because software bugs could be more expensive and dangerous. Let see the incident happen due to software bugs in the real world history in April 2015, due to software anomaly in Bloomberg Terminal at London, more than 300,000 traders affected on financial markets. Due to this the United Kingdom government postponed a Three Billion pound debt sale. In the Nissan cars due to software failure in the airbag sensor detector, the companies recalled over one million cars from the market. Due to software bugs in Amazon's third party retailers product price is reduced to one pound. And they have heavy money losses. In 2015 fighter plane F – 35 falls victim to a software bug. In 1994 China airlines airbus A300 crashed due to a software bug which killed 264 passenger. In the Software Development life cycle, software testing start from the first phase requirements collection and continue till the deployment of the software. Software Testing depends on the development model, for example in the waterfall model testing is conducted in the testing phase and in the incremental model testing done at the end of the application. So testing is done at any phase of Software Development Life Cycle. In the software testing it's hard to conclude when to stop the testing process of the product. No one can prerogative that the software or product is 100% tested perfectly. There are some criteria to stop the testing process. They are Execution of test case completely. Completion of functional and code coverage to a certain point. Fault detected below certain level and no high priority faults are detected.

II. Deadlines of Testing.

There are different types of software testing basically manual testing and automation testing. In manual testing, a tester performs test planning, test execution and reporting bugs manually by human efforts. Manual testing will run sequentially and it takes more time, human efforts and low accuracy with less expensive. Automation testing is a part of manual testing, the tester writes the test scripts to start the testing of the product. Automation testing can run at different machine in the similar time, it takes less time, high accuracy and more expensive than manual testing.

There are different methods used in the software testing they are Black-Box Testing, White-Box Testing and Grey-Box Testing. In the Black-Box Testing, the testers have knowledge of system

architecture and the tester test as a user interface by providing required inputs and monitoring the output without knowledge of internal source code. White-Box Testing also called as Glass Testing or Open-Box Testing. The testers should have detailed knowledge of internal logic and structure of the source code. When the tester identified the error or bug have to be check in the code and to correct the logic. Gray-Box Testing is a combination of both Black-Box Testing and White-Box Testing. The testers should have knowledge of internal logic and source code as well as the design documents and database. By this knowledge the tester can test better data and better test scenario.

There are different levels in software testing methods. The main methods are functional testing and non-functional testing. Functional testing involves to check the complete integration of system based on its business specification, functional testing carried by manual or Automata tool. Functional testing follows few steps before executing. They are to collect the Test Data based on the specification of the function. Consider business requirement are the inputs to functional testing. Find the output based on the functional specification of the function. Test Case execution. Observe actual and expected output observation.

There are various types of Functional testing they are Regression Testing, Unit Testing, Smoke Testing, Integration Testing, Interface Testing, System Testing & etc. Non-Functional testing is used to test the product quality like Performance, Reliability, Scalability but not Functionality of the product. Non-Functionality Testing starts after the completion of Functional Testing. Manual Testing in Non-Functional is Hard, automata tools used for Non-Functionality Testing which is easy and accuracy. There are various types of Non-Functionality testing's, they are Performance, Load Testing, Volume Testing, Stress Testing, Security Testing and etc. All manuscripts must be in English. These guidelines include complete descriptions of the fonts, spacing, and related information for producing your proceedings manuscripts.

III. Literature Survey

In the software engineering, software testing is a frequently occurrence due to continuous changes in the system. Regression testing is used to test those rapid changes in a system with past tested version. Due to these changes it's hard to retest all strategy because of huge test suite. Author proposed study on optimal solution to reduce test suite, in his approach computational intelligence based method is used to reduce the test suite. For optimizing single object based optimization used to find all the test cases that can detect fault are included in resultant test suite

Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing and the test case which do not detect the fault are not included in the test suite. Original test suite consists of fault revealing test cases and non-fault revealing test cases. Author shown four possibilities to include test cases based on fault detection with coverage optimization, the resultant test suite is precision and inclusiveness is achieved by including only test cases that can detect fault in regression testing and all other test cases not included in the resultant test suite. Safety parameter is used in control flow graph to verify the maximum coverage possibilities of code. But author found that the single objective based optimization computational intelligence safety reduction of test cases is not achieved as effectively[1].

In the regression testing number of test cases are larger in the test suite. So the test case redundancy is highly possible in the test suite. Due to test case redundancy test case execution cost is more and time taken to execute the redundancy test case is high. To avoid the redundancy the Author proposed decision table rule based test case reduction. In his method Author planning what to test and test data for expected result of the product. First author collects requirements specifications from the user and then condition/action deployment. And the author design decision table based on the condition what action to be done. In this stage if redundant decision table forms then author removed the redundant decision table. In the next stage after decision table created, now based on user specification requirement mapped with decision table rules are formed. In this stage redundant rules are found and removed. After removing the redundant rules now the final rules are irredundant and ready to test the products. As a result of this method author shown 33% of the test case redundancy observed and reduced. So it's shown due to test case redundancy it is more cost effective and time consuming efficient [2].

The cost of regression testing can be reduced by proper order test case selection and test case prioritization in terms of some criteria. Author studies shown that the cost cognizant additional greedy multi-objective optimization algorithm and multi objective genetic algorithm has a problem in finding better fault detection? Greedy and multi-objective genetic algorithm combination does not produce better results in terms of fault detection. Author proposed a new model to improve multi objective genetic algorithm and injecting diversity in genetic algorithm. During search process the test case in test suite by multi objective genetic algorithm in which injecting diversity, which is diversity based genetic algorithm. Diversity base genetic algorithm is based on the mechanics of orthogonal design and orthogonal evolution. By injecting individuals new orthogonal diversity is increased during the search process. As a result author shown

empirical study on eleven programs that outperforms on both the greedy algorithm and traditional multi objective genetic algorithm optimally and by diversity based genetic algorithm, fault detection rate is higher for same cost of test case execution compare to other algorithms [3].

Genetic algorithm used in regression testing for fault localization. Due to crossover mutation in the genetic algorithm, global population is not retaining its variations because mutation operation is violent. Author proposed new method to overcome above stated drawback, he combined genetic immune algorithm and artificial immune algorithm based up on their characteristics. Initially, the antigen is modified code for the analysis data flow on the control flow graph and form the binary encoding. Next is antibody represents test case that covers all the modified code and population represents the collection of test case. Affinity refers to distance between antigen and antibody in the program and then test case are converted in to binary codes. Affinity process to find concentration that represents similarities among test cases, with minimum degree of similarity and maximum diversity of test cases based up on concentration immune selection, cloning, crossover, mutation and clone inhibition. At last replace the population, antibody results and generating fault localization for regression test case. As a result of this approach author shown that the enhancement qualities of regression test case fault localization by combining Genetic Immune Algorithm and Artificial Immune Algorithm [4].

From the literature survey reference [1]-[4] its clearly conclude that there is no optimal solution to handle when the test case tie occurs.

IV. Problem Description

Regression Testing is one of the Testing process changes in software to make sure that the existing software still working with new changes. During the Regression testing, we need minimal number of test cases from already tested test suite that minimize the time and cost of the testing. There are many conventional techniques available for test case reduction. The conventional test case reduction techniques are Get split, Greedy and Coverall algorithm. In conventional techniques, most of the technique not effectively used for selecting the effective test cases from the test suite in the form of fault detection capability and does not handling test case tie during the reduction process. To overcome this problem, the proposed approach uses hybrid approach to select effective test cases as well as handle the test case which one is tie. Identifying test case tie and removing it will reduce the test cases to be test as well as reduce in cost and time to test the test case.

Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing

Block Diagram

Figure.1 Proposed Approach

Methodology&Implementation

Test Case Reduction Using Hybrid Approach

Algorithm.1 shows that proposed approach for test case reductions that consists of Greedy Loop and Genetic Loop.

Algorithm.1 Hybrid Algorithm

Hybrid (T[1...n], S[1...n])

For every $T_i \in T[1...n]$

For every $S_i \in S[1...n]$

If (S_i covered by T_i) then

Mark '1' in the coverage set.

Else

Mark '0' in the coverage set.

For every $T_i \in T[1...n]$

Count number of statement covered by T_i .

[Greedy Loop]

Select T_i which one covering more number of statements then

Mark '0' if the same statement covered by other test cases.

If more than one T_i covering same number of statement

Select all T_i and Mark '0' if the same statement covered by other test cases.

Store T_i in RTS

Repeat Greedy Loop until no one marked '1' in coverage set.

[Genetic Process]

Generate Initial population for tied test case based on coverage and HF.

Calculate Fitness value for each $T_i \in T[1 \dots n]$ and keep in Roulette wheel.

[Genetic Loop]

Select T_i from Roulette wheel.

Perform selection operation If output of selection == Target then select T_i otherwise Go to 4.3.3

Perform cross over If output of crossover == Target then select T_i otherwise Go to 4.3.4.

Perform mutation If output of mutation == Target then select T_i otherwise select any one T_i which one has highest fitness value and repeat step 4.3.

Store selected T_i in RTS

Return RTS.

Implementation

Sample Code For Testing

The source code has been taken for testing process in which the some statements are numbered and weightage of few statements are mentioned. The source code follows

Algorithm.2 Sample Code

CODE	Statement Number	Weightage
Function Max (num1, num2, num3)	-	-
{	-	-
If (num1 > num2) && (num1 > num3)	S7	-
{	-	-
Largest = num1;	S8	0.5
}	-	-
Else If (num2 > num1)	S9	-
&& (num2 > num3)		

Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing

Largest = num2;	S10	0.2
Else Largest = num3;	S11	0.7
Return (Largest);	-	-
}	-	-
 Function Total (num1, num2, num3)	-	-
{	-	-
If (num1 > num2)	S12	-
{	-	-
If (num1==num3)	S13	-
{	-	-
Total = num1+ num2;	S14	0.3
}	-	-
}	-	-
Else		
If(num3<=num2)	S15	-
{	-	-
Total=num1+num2+num3;	S16	0.5
}	-	-
Else	-	-
Total = num1;	S17	0.2
Return (Total);	-	-
}	-	-
 Void main ()	-	-
{	-	-
Int num1, num2, num3;	-	-
If (num1 > num2)	S1	-
If (num1 == num3)	S2	-
{	-	-

```

    Call max(num1, num2, num3);      S3      0.2
}
Else
    If (num1 < num3)                S4      -
    Call max(num1, num2, num3);      S5      0.7
Else
    Call Total (num1, num2, num3);   S6      0.4
}

```

Sample Test Data

The Table.1 shows list of test cases has been taken for testing the above source code initially. The table1 gives Test Id, Test Data and History Factor for every test case in which history factor represents most effective test cases which has been used in the previous testing process. More effective test cases have higher History Factor that calculated from previous project. The test case consideration follows

Table.1 Test Data and History Factor

TEST ID	TEST DATA	HISTORY FACTOR
T1	[1, 8, 4]	2
T2	[2, 16, 1]	6
T3	[2, 2, 8]	5
T4	[4, 6, 4]	1
T5	[7, 4, 4]	0
T6	[16, 1, 9]	8
T7	[3, 1, 3]	1
T8	[1, 1, 1]	0
T9	[9, 6, 5]	0
T10	[12, 2, 12]	3

Coverage Information for main function:

Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing

Table.2 shows list of the statements and functional statements are covered by initial test cases T1 to T10 in which, if statement or function covered by test case then it is marked as '1' otherwise '0'.

Table.2 Coverage Information

ID	STATEMENTS						FUNCTION Call	
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	Max	Total
T1 [1,8, 4]	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
T2 [2,16,1]	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
T3 [2,2, 8]	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0
T4 [4,6, 4]	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
T5 [7,4,4]	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
T6 [16,1,9]	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
T7 [3,1,3]	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0
T8 [1,1,1]	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
T9 [9,6,5]	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
T10 [12,2,12]	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0

Coverage Information for main, max and total function:

Table.3A, Table.3B and Table.3C shows list of the statements in main, max and Total function are covered by initial test cases T1 to T10 in which, if statement is covered by test case then it is marked as '1' otherwise '0'.

Table.3A Main Function Coverage Information

ID	MAIN					
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
T1	0	0	0	1	1	0
T2	0	0	0	0	0	1
T3	0	0	0	1	1	0
T4	0	0	0	0	0	1
T5	1	0	0	0	0	0
T6	1	0	0	0	0	0
T7	1	1	1	0	0	0
T8	0	0	0	0	0	1
T9	1	0	0	0	0	0
T10	1	1	1	0	0	0

Table.3B Max Function Coverage Information

ID	MAX				
	S7	S8	S9	S10	S11
T1	0	0	1	1	0
T2	0	0	0	0	0
T3	0	0	0	0	1
T4	0	0	0	0	0
T5	0	0	0	0	0
T6	0	0	0	0	0
T7	0	0	0	0	1
T8	0	0	0	0	0
T9	0	0	0	0	0
T10	0	0	0	0	1

Table.3C Total Function Coverage Information

ID	TOTAL
----	-------

Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing

	S12	S13	S14	S15	S16	S17
T1	0	0	0	0	0	0
T2	0	0	0	1	1	0
T3	0	0	0	0	0	0
T4	0	0	0	0	0	1
T5	0	0	0	0	0	0
T6	0	0	0	0	0	0
T7	0	0	0	0	0	0
T8	0	0	0	1	1	0
T9	0	0	0	0	0	0
T10	0	0	0	0	0	0

Initially Greedy approach has been used for test case reduction and then if there is any test case has tie during test case reduction then Genetic approach has been applied for handling test case tie to improving the TCR process. Table4 shows list of statement are covered by every test cases from test suite [T1...T10]. After finding coverage information, the weight map has been generated and Greedy approach used for selecting the test cases in which test case is selected which one has highest weight. The coverage information, weight mapping and selected test case by Greedy approach follows

Table.4 Weight Mapping 1

TEST CASE	STATEMENT COVERED
T1	4, 5, 9, 10
T2	6, 15, 16
T3	4, 5, 11
T4	6, 17
T5	1
T6	1
T7	1, 2, 3, 11
T8	6, 15, 16
T9	1

T10	1, 2, 3, 11
-----	-------------

Weight map calculated by total number of statement covered by test case. In Table 4, four statements covered by T1, three statements by T2 and so on. Then highest weight 4 is selected from the weight mapping sequence and corresponding test case T1 is selected. The weight mapping follows Weight mapping: 4, 3, 3, 2, 1, 1, 4, 3, 1, 4

Selected test case: T1

In Table 5 shows that the statements which are covered by selected test case T1 that statements are marked as '0'. The table follows

Table.5 Weight Mapping 2

TEST CASE	STATEMENT COVERED
T1	0, 0, 0, 0
T2	6, 15, 16
T3	0, 0, 11
T4	6, 17
T5	1
T6	1
T7	1, 2, 3, 11
T8	6, 15, 16
T9	1
T10	1, 2, 3, 11

Weight Map: 0, 3, 1, 2, 1, 1, 4, 3, 1, 4

Selected Test cases: T7 and T10

From the Table.5 weight map two test cases T7 and T10 are selected, because both test cases having same weight as well as covering same statements. To handle this test case tie, both test case selected and optimized in the further process with help of genetic algorithm. This process will continue until all the statements covered by selected test cases. The further reduction process follows

Table.6 Weight Mapping 3

TEST CASE	STATEMENT COVERED
T1	0, 0, 0, 0

Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing

T2	6, 15, 16
T3	0, 0, 0
T4	6, 17
T5	0
T6	0
T7	0, 0, 0, 0
T8	6, 15, 16
T9	0
T10	0, 0, 0, 0

Weight Mapping: 0, 3, 0, 2, 0, 0, 0, 3, 0, 0

Selected Test Case: T2 and T8

Table.7 Weight Mapping 4

TEST CASE	STATEMENT COVERED
T1	0, 0, 0, 0
T2	0, 0, 0
T3	0, 0, 0
T4	0, 17
T5	0
T6	0
T7	0, 0, 0, 0
T8	0, 0, 0
T9	0
T10	0, 0, 0, 0

Weight Mapping: 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0

Selected test Case: T4

The final selected test cases in TCR suite are: T1, [T7, T10], [T2, T8], T4. In the selected test cases there is two pair of test case ties. The tie test cases are [T7, T10] and [T2, T8]. Now Genetic loop has been used to select the 75% test cases from which test case tie in the TCR suite.

For Genetic Loop, we have considered the test cases T7, T10, T8, T2 because T7 & T10 tied and T2 & T8 are tied. Now Genetic loop has been applied to select the 75% of test cases from above considered test cases. In the Genetic loop we have generated initial population for every test cases based on its coverage and history factor. In the Initial population generation, if any statement covered by test case than it Gene marked as '1' otherwise '0'. In the Table.8 first 17 bits represent statement coverage information and last four bit represent binary equivalent of history factor of the test case.

Table.8Initial Population

Test ID	T2	T7	T8	T10
I N I T I A L P O P U L A T I O N	0	1	0	1
	0	1	0	1
	0	1	0	1
	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0
	1	0	1	0
	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0
	0	1	0	1
	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0
	1	0	1	0
	1	0	1	0
	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0
1	0	0	0	
1	0	0	1	
0	1	0	1	

Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing

Next step of the Genetic loop is Fitness value calculation for all the test cases. In this step, the fitness value calculated by formula

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (\text{Gene}_i \times W_i) \quad (1)$$

Here ‘W’ (Weight) represents weight of the statement given in Table.1 and weightage of first Gene of history factor is 0.8, second weightage is 0.4, third weightage is 0.2 and the fourth weightage is 0.1 has been considered. The Fitness value follows

Table.9 Fitness Value

TES T ID	FITNESS VALUE
T2	$(1 \times 0.4) + (1 \times 0.5) + (1 \times 0.5) + (1 \times 0.4) + (1 \times 0.2) = 2.0$
T7	$(1 \times 0.2) + (1 \times 0.2) + (1 \times 0.2) + (1 \times 0.7) + (1 \times 0.1) = 1.4$
T8	$(1 \times 0.4) + (1 \times 0.5) + (1 \times 0.5) = 1.4$
T10	$(1 \times 0.2) + (1 \times 0.2) + (1 \times 0.2) + (1 \times 0.7) = 1.3$

Next step of the Genetic loop is Selection. Initially, Selection loop selects any two test cases from the Roulette wheel. Assume T7 and T10 has selected from Roulette wheel in the first iteration of selection loop. Then further steps follows

Table.10 TC Combination

T7	T10	OR
1	1	1
1	1	1
1	1	1
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
1	0	1
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
1	0	1
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	1	1
1	1	1

Before combining T7 with T10, our coverage percentage is 23.80. After combining with T7 and T10 our coverage percentage improved from 23.80 to 28.56. But still our coverage percentage is not meeting our target percentage (50%). So we need crossover loop for next level optimization in which 4th& 5th bit of T7 and 11th&12th bit has been considered for crossover operation. The crossover step shown in Table.11.

Table.11 TC Cross Over

Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing

T7	T10	OR
1	1	1
1	1	1
1	1	1
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
1	1	1
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
0	1	1
1	1	1

Before crossover of T7 with T10, our coverage percentage is 28.56. After crossover, our coverage percentage improved from 28.56 to 33.33. But still our coverage percentage is not meeting our target percentage (50%). So we need mutation loop for next level optimization in which ‘0’ as ‘1’ and vice versa. Here 8th and 9th bit has been considered from crossover output for mutation operation. The mutation step shown in Table.12.

Table.12 TC Mutation

OR
1

1
1
0
0
0
1
1
1
0
1
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
0
1
1

Before mutation our coverage percentage is 33.33. After mutation, our coverage percentage improved from 33.33 to 42.85. But still our coverage percentage is not meeting our target percentage (50%). At end of this iteration, both combination of T7 & T10 has not reached our target. So highest Fitness value test case T7 is retained and one new test case selected from Roulette wheel for further optimization to reach our target. These Genetic loops repeat the process until 75% of test cases are retained. Suppose all combination of test cases not meet our target criteria then the target criteria reduced and Genetic loop will be initiated for new target. At end of Genetic loop the selected test cases are T10, T2 and T7. The final selected test cases using combination of Greedy and Genetic Algorithm are T1, T10, T2, T4 and T7.

Result Analysis

Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing

In Figure.2 shown that the performance of basic Greedy algorithm. In the performance chart X-axis represent Test Case ID and Y-axis represent Number of Statements covered. Chart shows total six number of test case selected from test suite and covering the 12 statement that needs execution of all six test cases because those 12statements covered after execution of last test case T4.

Figure.2 Basic Greedy Approach

Figure.3 shows that the performances of Hybrid approach. In the performance chart X-axis represent Test Case ID and Y-axis represent Number of Statements covered. The performance chart shows five test cases selected from test suite and covering 12 statements.

The Basic Greedy approach covered 12 statements after execution of fifth test case. From the analysis of Greedy and Hybrid approach, we can conclude that our proposed approach is better than Basic Greedy approach in terms of covering the statement as earlier as possible and reducing number of test cases in the test suite. Hybrid approach proves that it takes less time in testing to cover same number of statement which covered in basic greedy Algorithm and also Hybrid approach will reduce the testing Cost.

Figure.3 Hybrid Approach (Greedy+Genetic)

V. Conclusion and Future

In this research we have introduced new proposed model for test case reduction and prioritization. To reduce number of test cases in the test suite, Hybrid approach for has been used. Finally result of Hybrid approach has compared with Basic Greedy approach and this research proved that performance of Hybrid approach is better than Basic Greedy approach for effective test case selection. In this Hybrid approach, only 25% of test cases are eliminated from tied test suite but still there is some tied test cases in the reduction test suite that degrades performance of the testing during the test case prioritization. In future, this research going to focus on effective test case prioritization for tied test case instead of random prioritization.

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Hybrid data approach for selecting effective test cases during the regression testing

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